

Reinterpretation and Re-Contextualisation of Badagry's Ogu Music in *Avale*: Ethnomusicological and Artistic Convergence in a Trans-Local and Trans-Genre Collaborative Music Production

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Abstract. The main aim of applied ethnomusicology is to solve concrete social problems through musical advocacy and intervention. However, a few scholars, including Hofman (2010), have contested the essence of applied ethnomusicology, arguing that the production of knowledge in the field of ethnomusicology has always inspired solutions to societal problems. In other words, ethnomusicology has always been applied. Based on the learnings from the production of *Avale*, a collaborative album involving the author and Gogoke, a musical ensemble from Badagry (Lagos State, Nigeria), this paper argues that applied works are essential in underserved areas and marginalized communities. Furthermore, the article highlights the structural exclusion of the individuals and communities that produce research data from epistemic communities nested within the academy, which privileges Western ideation and end reporting over indigenous knowledge. More so, this paper addresses the exclusivity of epistemic communities using the study's model of interventionist collaboration, which is beneficial to researchers and their community partners. The paper concludes that applied ethnomusicology could better fulfil its aim of solving social problems with negotiated acts of reciprocity. The collaboration between indigenous Ogu musicians and the author in this study is cited as an inclusive knowledge creation method. The study results validate and expand Harrison's (2012; 2014) and Summit's (2015) groundwork on applied ethnomusicology and suggest new frames for the academic study of indigenous musics.

Is academic research equal to 'using and dumping'? A vignette on the negotiations that birthed *Avale*

At the commencement of my doctoral fieldwork in November 2017, I aimed to collect and analyze samples of traditional Ogu songs from Badagry, a peripheral border town in Lagos State, Nigeria, next to the Republic of Benin. Although Ogu people on either side of the international border share similar characteristics, their different citizenships and colonial histories contribute to the nuances in expressions and the subtle variations in their trajectories of artistic development. Because of this, a comparative study of musical practices in Badagry (Nigeria) and Porto Novo (Republic of Benin) was within my purview as I aimed to compose new songs based on Ogu musical idioms. First, the material living condition of the research participants, and later, the negotiation of a mutually beneficial venture, compelled remarkable serendipity on the study. Some members of Gogoke (the case study band based in Igbogbele, a community close to the Owode border in Badagry) expressed mistrust in the study, which necessitated a negotiation.

The negotiation culminated in my collaboration with the local musicians to reimagine and document their music, as a replacement for the composition component of my research. I refer to this collaborative music production as a *recontextualisation* of Gogoke's music. The process changes the traditional format and contexts through which the music is presented and adds popular and widely spread instrumentation and aesthetics in ways that I will discuss later. Inadvertently, the study was compelled to change from only focusing on knowledge creation to advocating for its participants. Regarding the collaboration, the primary thing I could contribute was my skill set, being knowledgeable in studio production and the arrangement of music. If applied ethnomusicology is about creating uses for ethnomusicological research beyond the academy's goal of expanding the knowledge about "people making music" (Titon 2015:4), then this switch in my research focus reflects the difference between Ethnomusicology and Applied Ethnomusicology. The negotiation leading to the change in focus would be insightful in highlighting the participants' perception of a study that does not directly benefit them.

My plan to study Gogoke was met by different responses from the band members, ranging from appreciation and joy to threats of mysterious unpleasant occurrences if my motive was wrong. A 'wrong motive' includes the use of the band's musical ideas for personal gains without giving back to them. One of the band members said:

[...] we don't know your mind yet and you also don't know our mind concerning you. God is the only one who knows our intentions. Just let us know your plans, and we won't disappoint you. We will only disappoint if we sense that we are being used – as an instrument – and dumped. That is what we are trying to avoid. That is all I have to say. (Gogoke member, November 10, 2017. The comment was made in Yoruba and translated to English by the author).

Another band member added:

I want to support what the previous speaker said. Some people do that [referring to using and dumping], and I have revolted against such moves in the past. I personally even said we would not go into any project with you; that we should not allow you to study us, but the other band members pacified me. My point exactly is to prevent you from collecting all these materials and in the future, you feel all that you have collected is enough, and you go ahead to use them without us. Forget it! It won't work! It won't work, and your progress will be [supernaturally] impeded. The instruments we use are [made of] *Ogun* [the Yoruba tutelary deity in charge of metal works, and the same word is sometimes used to refer to metal itself] and we can use it to curse [cast spells on] people. (Gogoke member, November 10, 2017. The comment was made in Yoruba and translated to English by author).

In this context, *Ogun*, the Yoruba deity believed to control the realm of creativity, is often invoked to avenge injustice within the creative and other related spheres. Hence, recourse

to *Ogun* seemed necessary in advocating for mutually beneficial research. This was my “trial by fire,” to borrow Dan Bendrups’ words (2015: 78). However, it is a typical experience among researchers working in underserved, marginalized and disempowered communities. At this point, it became clear to me that my study would be better received if designed to benefit the case study band. The onus then lay on me to critically interrogate the interventions that the research participants consider beneficial.

As Nyamnjoh noted, researchers’ “interests may not intersect or coincide with” those of their community partners (2017: 366). Hence the need to scrutinise Gogoke band members’ expectations through negotiations. Negotiations with Gogoke revealed that the primary desire of the band, which seemed largely elusive, was to document their songs on an album. Accordingly, we agreed that it was necessary to produce these songs to suit some modern sound recording preferences. For instance, the traditional medley format of presentation, often leading to extended performance durations, may not be suitable since one of the goals of recontextualising the songs is possible radio airplay. I will return to discuss the choices made in producing Gogoke’s songs and the reason for those choices.

The two-year duration of our collaborative project was marked by excitement as well as skepticism and tepidity among the band members, and only at the repatriation of the finalized recordings were some of the band members convinced of the benignity of the study.

For me, the major learnings from this experience are:

1. The observation and drawing of conclusions that took place in this study were mutual and multidirectional between the researcher and the case study band. In other words, as I studied Gogoke, its members also observed me, made speculations and conclusions about my intentions, and they would later reveal their ‘findings’ after I repatriated the mixed versions of the studio-recorded music to the band.
2. In the kind of context described above, studying a group of people for the mere purpose of contributing to academic knowledge may not suffice to garner the cooperation of participants. Besides, collecting and using data for scholarly purposes may be perceived as exploiting the study participants or, in the words of Gogoke members, “using and dumping” them.

While focusing on the second learning, this article is positioned within the applied ethnomusicological discourse on artistic intervention for social and economic change, and it argues that applied works in certain contexts are necessities, without which the research may not only lose credibility, but the researcher also risks breaching the trust of the participants and this may hinder further studies among them. Given this, the paper also expands the definition of Applied Ethnomusicology and its application based on the nuances of the study site.

Ethnomusicological and artistic convergence in the production of *Avale*

The production of the collaborative album *Avale* began in November 2017. The album would feature five of Gogoke's original compositions, which are traditionally performed with monophonic call-and-response singing, nested within a dense Ogu percussion section. As mentioned earlier, these songs are presented in a medley form, enhanced by the cyclical structure of Ogu dance genres, in their traditional performance contexts. One of the first creative choices in recontextualizing Gogoke's music was to separate these songs into shorter individual pieces of not more than five minutes each. This suits the popular and trans-local preference for songs with short durations, thus enhancing Gogoke's chances of getting radio play. The strategy for recording these songs was for Gogoke to perform these songs live, albeit individually, in a recording studio in Badagry. Following this, I studied the pieces for about a year before embarking on the musical arrangements for additional popular musical instruments. The following characteristics of Gogoke's music, and by extension, Ogu music, are remarkable:

- The singing is monophonic and without any vocal harmony
- The instrumentation is primarily percussive, without any tonal instrument.
- The time is fluid, hemiolic, and kaleidoscopic – time in Ogu music may be interpreted and understood differently by different musicians, depending on their musical backgrounds and influences.
- The inherent form of the music is wave-like, beginning with vocal recitative, followed by the addition of *ogan* (bell) pattern. The other (auxiliary) drums are added one after the other and the culmination of each wave-like section is highlighted by improvised and infectious rhythms on *pawhle* (the lead drum). I will return to discuss this wave-like musical form later.

The band gave me the leeway to decide on the non-Ogu instruments to add and the suitable arrangements for these instruments, following a mutual agreement to reform Gogoke's music. The reasoning behind the additional arrangements is captured in Turino's (2000: 106) framework of *modernist reformism*, which entails creating a "viable" style "for cosmopolitan audiences" through the blending of traditional genres and popular musical aesthetics. Thus, the emergent sound could serve as a nexus, drawing on a broader audience. This has often led to the birth of genres specific to their origin yet relatable further afield. Accordingly, I made additional arrangements for a guitar, a bass, and a horn section.

In departing from the patterns of syncretism through which many popular Africa genres have developed fortuitously, I was courteous to centralize the essence of the band's music in the emergent composite sound – its infectious rhythms, vocal style, and other typical Ogu musical sensibilities. I did this to ensure that the reformed music remains relatable to the more conservative listeners among Badagry's Ogu people. At the same time, the music production had to be negotiated around the social values of Ogu people, such as opening performances with songs that pay homage to the powers that be. In other words, the

creative choices in recontextualizing Gogoke's music had to be cognizant of both musical and social values inherent in Ogu musical culture. I examine these next.

In addition to the musical characteristics highlighted earlier, socio-cultural and spiritual underpinnings are essential considerations in reimagining and recontextualizing Ogu music. For instance, as earlier stated, every Ogu album or live performance must begin with homage-paying, failing which the band risks disapproval within its local context. Given this, the track, *Avale* (literally: homage), was suitable as the first song and the title of Gogoke's debut album.

On the other hand, a musical consideration led to my preference for a guitar over a piano in recontextualizing Gogoke's music, since the latter would likely be too imposing on the music. As Gogoke's songs are devoid of harmony, this would be an area of intervention that could create a broader appeal for the music. Furthermore, minimal additional rhythm instruments would be required if Gogoke's dense percussion were to be central in the composite sound. Hence, I added only the electric guitar and bass to the rhythm section. Reflexivity, in this instance, would include accounting for my preference for extended harmony and the horn section textures on different songs. These preferences underscore my enculturation, travels and, education, among other influences, which have informed my eclectic musicality. Having experienced Ogu music from childhood, I have also resided in various South African cities. The longest as of the time of writing was my nine-year stay in Cape Town. In addition, I have received formal training as a trumpeter and in jazz arrangement. Hence, my arrangements would reflect the subtleties of my cosmopolitan worldview. Thus, the guitar and bass defined the chord changes, which serve as a harmonic foundation for additional layers. A horn section, varying from two to six wind instruments (flute, trumpet, trombone, and alto, tenor, and baritone saxophones), complement the vocal parts by tastefully filling vocal intervals. On the other hand, the horn section also adds contrasting melodic materials as in jazz (big band) soli sections. In a nutshell, my additions were minimal rhythm section instruments, defining my composed harmony to the songs; and a complementary horn section, positioned in conversation with the vocal melodies and introducing contrasting melodic materials.

The production of *Avale* animates Harrison's (2014:21) suggestion that an applied ethnomusicologist is a mediator between cultures. I would add that recontextualizing traditional musical practices derived from the context described thus far requires a mediator who is both musically inclined and knowledgeable about the cultural specifics and nuances of the musical worlds being mediated. In the case of *Avale*, it took an ethnomusicologist with jazz training to create a musical nexus accessible both on the local scene in Badagry and to a trans-local and digital listening audience (see Louise Meintjes 2003, for an argument for the importance of music production as an avenue for trans-local accessibility of indigenous musics). To this end, *Avale* foregrounded a new era in the economics of Gogoke's performances as it has become a bargaining tool for gigs, seeking further sponsorship and publishing deals, and merchandise at the band's live performances. As Summit (2015:207-8)

noted, interventions are likely to fail, despite a researcher's passion and enthusiasm, without a full contextual understanding. In a nutshell, a collaborative music production like *Avale* requires a convergence of ethnomusicological and artistic expertise. Hence, in keeping with Pettan (2015: 30), I argue that an in-depth understanding of cultural contexts is essential for advocacy and collaborative works. That said, I turn now to examine further how we negotiated the mutually beneficial use of the study in ways that were benign and not mere exploitation of a traditional band by a researcher in a privileged position.

Towards a more inclusive definition of applied ethnomusicology

Titon (2015) defined applied ethnomusicology as "music-centred intervention in a particular community whose purpose is to benefit that community." The Study Group on Applied Ethnomusicology of the ICTM defines applied ethnomusicology as "the approach, guided by principles of social responsibility, which extends the usual academic goal of broadening and deepening knowledge and understanding toward solving concrete problems and toward working both inside and beyond typical academic contexts" (ICTM 2014, quoted in Harrison 2014:18). What would "social responsibility" mean in Igbogbele, an underserved community? What would it mean to "benefit" Gogoke? How may applied ethnomusicology solve some of the concrete day-to-day problems of Gogoke band? According to Titon (2015), at least three realms of intervention are plausible:

- creating a benefit for them **musically** (improve their musical understanding within the context of modern-day reality)
- **cultural benefit** (to preserve their music, which means a lot to them, in a manner that they can pass on to their children)
- creating an **economic advantage** (repatriating their music in a manner that can be sold to generate some income and also increase their chances of sponsorship).

Avale's contribution in these three realms is engendered by the researcher's vulnerability and willingness to understand what the band members consider appropriate.

Following the comments of the band members discussed earlier and the subsequent negotiation of a mutually beneficial project, *Avale* became symbolic of an opportunity to document Gogoke's original compositions, distribute them beyond the local scene, and make economic gains. Accordingly, if this expectation was not met, chances are they would view the study as "using and dumping" them. Given this, applied ethnomusicology in the context described so far must also be cognizant of the expectations of the community. While ethnomusicologists may not be able to meet all the expectations of their study participants, it is essential to know what those expectations are. There is a level of humility or in Summit's (2015:211) word "vulnerability" required from researchers who must be willing to lay aside preconceived ideas of suitable interventions to understand what the study participants consider appropriate.

Conversely, as *Avale* revealed, researchers' vulnerability is potentially more rewarding to researchers than their studied communities. Summit (2015:225) further remarked that "[w]hile advocacy is often understood as a means to impact the other, in unexpected ways, it is the advocate who is transformed by this work." At the repatriation of *Avale* to the band, Gogoke members were thankful for the 'help' I had rendered, whereas, the project had transformed me and shaped my career path in ways I least expected when it began. The point to be made here is that ethnomusicological advocacy is not a linear process but a multilateral one in which the studied communities help to shape researchers' careers and outlooks.

As Pettan (2015:20) noted, the definitions of applied ethnomusicology vary with time, place, traditions, and preferences of both the studied and researcher. Based on my learnings from the production of *Avale*, applied ethnomusicology in the socio-cultural context of Gogoke band involved a researcher's collaboration with a local community to solve specific problems of the community, on the one hand, and some of the researcher's problems, on the other hand. The following section highlights how *Avale* helped solve some of my academic problems and brought about insights regarding the privileging of researchers in the knowledge creation process.

Knowledge creation is not exclusive to the academy

The process of data collection, studio recording, and research writing on *Avale* revealed that epistemic communities nested within the academy privilege Western ideation and end reporting over indigenous knowledge. Besides, the current reward structure of the academy means little to community practitioners and thus technically excludes and takes advantage of them. I cite an example.

Jeremiah Tonukunme is the bandleader of Gogoke, and my discussion with him revealed a wealth of pedagogical practices and conceptualization of musical ideas that aid aurality. He used the metaphor of a wave, which I mentioned earlier, in describing the form of their music, and that is a concept easily understandable by musicians in Igbogbele, which is located near the Atlantic coast in Badagry. Other indigenous ideations include the use of non-lexical syllables in teaching and communicating drum patterns, and the use of vocables called *Asha* in local parlance, at the dance sections, which mark the culmination of each musical 'wave.'

The pattern has been that a scholar writes these ideas, creates concepts to capture them, and gets rewarded with a doctorate, while mentioning the individuals who gave the information marginally in the acknowledgements, list of interviews, and in-text references. This seems an insufficient reward for a contribution of this magnitude, and in fact, as the study has shown, listing such individuals as co-authors may not suffice. This is not to be simplistic or belittle academic rigors but to highlight the enormity of the contributions of the people we study to knowledge production, and to posit that community collaborators are

often inadequately recognized and rewarded for their contributions. On further investigation, one would see that the individuals who gave these ideas are hardly the sole authors. Instead, some ideas emerge over time and in communal spaces. This collective creation contrasts the individuality stressed in the academy. A question arises: how do we reward a community for its ideas? By the way, the community may have a different value system from that of the academic world (Nyamnjoh 2017).

Again, I am drawn to view the community projects done by academics not as a favor, but a compensation for the contribution of community members, for without the community, the academic field of ethnomusicology will not exist. Titon (2015:22) alluded to this when he remarked that the field of ethnomusicology had benefited more from external circumstances, including the gain in currency of world music and accepting of cultural diversity and pluralism in society than from its positioning as a research science. In the context of Igbogbele Badagry, "social responsibility" could mean, among other things, the production of *Avale* CDs which could be used to raise some funds for the band and better integrate them into the modernist-capitalist system. Otherwise, the band members may feel used, even after mentioning their names in the research writing. In contrast with a study that only focuses on increasing academic knowledge, collaborations in the manner of *Avale* production seem symbiotic (see Van Buren 2010: 219 for a remark on the need for academics to look for ways of benefiting and serving their studied communities more through collaborations and in ways that will empower the studied).

Conclusion

This research report attempts to interpret the definition of applied ethnomusicology within the context of Igbogbele Badagry, Lagos Nigeria. I invite researchers to critically consider this method of advocacy and see how it may be applied in similar contexts in other parts of Africa and possibly other parts of the world. The paper highlights that the people we study contribute so much and they deserve more reward than acknowledgments and inclusion in our academic outputs, which are more beneficial to the researcher. I also argue that the knowledge gathered from individuals is often a product of communal creation (see also Agawu 2016 for further illustration of communal creation of African musics). Given this, I recommend that the type of applied ethnomusicology in underserved communities should be accompanied by community projects that outlive the tenure of the research project and benefit more people than the individual who gave the information. If everyone entering applied ethnomusicology goes in with that understanding, our research will be better received, and we will benefit a lot more from the communities we study. Accordingly, I suggest that applied works should begin with negotiations of what is considered suitable as acts of reciprocity, and as I found, this was a pathway to ensuring Gogoke's commitment to the study (see also Dan Bendrups 2015: 79). In a nutshell, this paper is itself an advocacy for better inclusion of practitioners, who provide the essence of our outputs, in the academy

through a structural change and community projects, which is a necessity rather than a favor dependent on the goodwill of the researcher.

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